

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers,

welcome to the third issue of volume six. I want to thank all authors for their contributions and the editorial board for their review effort. I hope you will enjoy the papers.

This issue contains 7 articles: P. A. Carlson: Wonders of the Invisible Workplace: IT and Process Reinvention; I. Antoniou, M. Reeve, V. Stenning: The Information Society as a Complex System; W. D. Schindel, G. M. Rogers: Methodologies and Tools For Continuous Improvement of Systems; S. Thies: Coffein: Construction and Presentation of Design Knowledge; R. K. Hessley, D. L. Morris, Jr., M.R. R. Mueller: Integrated Applications of Electronic Structure Computations in the Undergraduate Chemistry Curriculum; D. W. Fellner, M. Zens: Electronic Submission, Managing and Approval of Grant Proposals at the German Research Foundation based on Standard Internet and Office Tools; D. W. Fellner, M. Zens: Perceptions about Internet Use by Teaching Faculty at Small Christian Colleges and Universities

Yours sincerely,

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